

PHRASEOLOGICAL EXPRESSION REPRESENTING THE CONCEPT OF “RICHNESS” IN UZBEK LANGUAGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13927425>

Annotation. This article explores the concept of “richness” in terms of cognitive linguistics. The study analyzes phraseological phrases associated with the concept of “richness” formed in Uzbek language. It explores the linguistic and cultural conceptual landscape expressed through phraseological phrases in Uzbek language.

Key words: Cognitive linguistics, conceptual landscape, concept, phraseological concept, richness.

By the start of the 21st century, it had become one of the advancing directions within the discipline. The emergence of cognitive linguistics is closely tied to the research conducted by American scholars such as J. Miller, J. Bruner, G. Lakoff, R. Langacker, and R. Jackendoff. Cognitive linguistics is a field that examines the relationships between language and human consciousness, exploring the role of language in conceptualizing the world and its connection with an individual's cognitive abilities, as well as the forms of interaction between these elements. The concept of conceptualization, which derives from cognitive linguistics, refers to the process of identifying a set of cognitive properties associated with the phenomena and processes of the world, thereby providing an individual with a defined understanding of a particular concept. This conceptualization process also involves the ability to recall these concepts, imbue them with new information, and distinguish them from other phenomena and processes.

The concept, which serves as the fundamental unit of thought, is based on the synthesis of generalized information, mental imagery, and linguistic meaning. The formation of a concept begins with the emergence of an individual mental image and culminates in the development of linguistic units to represent that conceptual understanding [1;17]. Phraseological units play a crucial role in constructing the linguistic picture of the world. These fixed expressions serve as a mirror, reflecting the life, characteristics, and conceptual understanding of a particular nation or culture [2;15]. Phraseological units not only describe

situations but also evaluate and respond to them, providing valuable insights into the worldview of the language community.

Given the significance of phraseological expressions in shaping the linguistic and conceptual worldview, the exploration of their national-cultural identity is a crucial area of study. This research aligns with the broader domains of “Language and Thought”, which have become increasingly relevant in modern linguistics. The examination of phraseological units within the framework of concept formation is, therefore, a timely and valuable line of inquiry.

The phrase “the knife is on oil” is an idiomatic expression that suggests a person's lifestyle is full and prosperous. In this context, the word “oil” refers to the fatty substance found in the tissues of livestock and some animals [3;233]. The use of this imagery implies a state of material well-being and sufficiency.

The expression “one can reach where one's hand reaches” is an idiomatic phrase that suggests a person has great faith and confidence in their abilities. In this sentence, the author has used two synonymous or similar phrases in succession to strengthen the meaning of the phraseological expression. The phrase “the arm was long enough to reach anywhere” reinforces the idea of extensive reach and capability [4;136].

Another idiomatic expression used in the text is “the sun has touched (his back)”, which means that a person has come out into the light and their work has progressed. This metaphorical phrase conveys a sense of achievement and advancement.

The phrase “to stay under money (or profit)” means to earn a lot of money or profit. Similarly, “to be buried in money (profit)” expresses the idea of having an abundance of wealth or profit. If your presentation is well-received by the conference participants, you may become a regular participant, which could lead to significant financial gains, meaning you could “get stuck on the bottom of the money” [5].

The phrase “Bread is whole” suggests that a person is sufficient, well-fed, prosperous, and lacking in nothing. The statement “The barber is the world, this world will not be despised. His bread is whole all the time” [6;116] implies that the person has a comfortable and secure existence, where their basic needs are consistently met. The expression “one shirt is two” indicates that a person's material conditions have improved, and they have become wealthy. The statement “Now it's over! One dress became two!” [7;4] emphasizes this idea of a person's transition from a more modest state to a more prosperous one.

Summary. Phrases such as “stay under the money (or profit),” “reach where you can reach”, and “before you eat, when you don't eat” are semantically similar to expression who have long been considered cultural brothers, share some common conceptualizations of wealth and prosperity. Uzbek expressions related to “richness” tend to convey more material and domestic notions. As mentioned in the introduction, each nation and people have both similar and distinct aspects based on their way of life, thinking, worldview, traditions, and customs. The research on phraseological expressions within the concept of “richness” provides a basis for understanding these underlying cultural the Uzbek nation.

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